

LEXICAL-SEMANTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF WORDS ADAPTED FROM ENGLISH TO UZBEKI

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Abstract: This article discusses the lexical-semantic features of words adopted from English to Uzbek. Also, in linguistics, detailed information about lexical-semantic features of the language is presented.

Key words: Linguistics, lexical-semantic feature, English language, Uzbek language, scientific analysis, theory.

The words transferred from English to Uzbek have not been studied separately either in Uzbek linguistics or in German studies.¹ brochure is available. This brochure, created as a result of the research work, covers all Germanic languages (English, German, Dutch, Scottish, Dutch, Icelandic, Swedish, Norwegian, Danish) and discusses the words transferred from them to the Uzbek language through the Ruz language. But the author did not have the opportunity to find all the words from English to Uzbek. That is why he transferred 150 words from English to Uzbek², shows that.

It has been more than 20 years since the pamphlet was published. During this period, great changes took place in the social system. The former Union disbanded. Instead, independent states emerged. In particular, the Republic of Uzbekistan achieved its independence and established diplomatic relations with the most developed countries of the world, such as America, England, Germany, and France, and started cooperation with them. joint ventures and large factories were established in the region. Of course, such free, friendly and direct cooperation is also reflected in languages. If a few years ago English words were assimilated into Uzbek through Russian, in the next few years, thanks to independence and direct cooperation, English words were transferred to Uzbek, and Uzbek words were directly transferred to English. For example, Uzbek words such as "Oliy Majlis", "Obad Mahalla", "Tharin", "Ghoza", "Halal", "Yonbosh", "Chala" are freely used in English. or the English that is actively used in Uzbek language "computer, disk, file, slide, printer, chisel, grader, bulldozer, broiler, iceberg, pullover, barter, business, tennis, sport, champion, trust, concern, conveyor" words like

According to our calculations, there are about 300 English words and phrases related to the computer and its technology that are used in the Uzbek language today. If we divide the English words in the Uzbek language into thematic groups, we can see that their fields of application have different characteristics:

- ❖ Words related to the socio-political sphere: congressman, laborer, lord, conservative chamber, trade union, chair, junker, chartism, chartist, blockade, boycott, press conference, press bureau;

¹ Jumaniozov O. Acquisitions of Germanic languages in the Uzbek language. Tashkent, 1987. p 45.

² Jumaniozov O. Acquisitions of Germanic languages in the Uzbek language. Tashkent, 1987. p 4.

- ❖ Regarding science, its various branches: folklore, detective, pamphlet, distribution, descriptive, humor, humorist, ryegrass, transistor, laser, resistor, kangaroo, gorilla, gulfstream, watt, bulldog, broiler, iceberg.
- ❖ Technical, first of all, computer terms: internet, computer display, file, diskette, printer, chisel, combine, scraper, speedometer, escalator, excavator, frazer, tractor, film, grader, bulldozer, antifreeze.
- ❖ Fabric, clothing and accessories: sweater, pullover, shorts, dryer, pajamas, jacket, covercoat, shampoo, jersey, sweater, velvet, breeches, lint, linter, mackintosh.
- ❖ Trade jobs and currencies: marketing, barter, export, import, supermarket, manager, management, monitoring, shilling, sterling, investor, investment, dollar, business, businessman, bar, bartender, bankrupt.
- ❖ Words related to art, music, game, recreation: twist, foxtrot, shake, clown, rock-n-roll, show, designer, jazz, hobby, music hall.
- ❖ Culinary and drink words: cake, service, liver, rum, pudding, cocktail, whiskey.
- ❖ Words and terms related to sports: sport, champion, championship, hockey, football, basketball, volleyball, start, finish, trainer, tennis, sportsman, ring, knockout, knockdown, record, round, match, cross, goal, goalkeeper, handball, water polo, boots, boxing, boxer, butterfly, badminton, out.
- ❖ Words expressing concepts related to place, building, vessel: park, square, region, club, office, container, comfort, camping, tunnel, station, airport, car park, aero club, canister, bunker.
- ❖ Words related to military work, military equipment: tank, sniper, revolver, radar, midshipman.
- ❖ Words related to industry, construction and typography: cottage, offset, veranda, wattman, concern, conveyor, trust.
- ❖ Words and phrases related to transport: express, bus, airbus, trolleybus, tram, liner, stewardess, nipple, elevator, carter, dispatcher, buffer.
- ❖ Terms representing people of different professions and categories: reporter, interviewer, gentleman, raid, leader, racketeer, farmer.
- ❖ Words related to seafaring, ship and steamer: cutter, yacht, trawler, tanker, tramp, boatsman.
- ❖ Medical and veterinary words: sinusitis, brucellosis, wilt, vegetarian, blockade.

So, to sum up, the words adopted from English to Uzbek are divided into different groups according to the fields of application, and each of them has its own lexical-semantic character.

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